

Analysis of High School Students' Critical Thinking Level Based on Logical Arguments

Yovita Yuliana Gunawan^{1*}, Sarwanto², Fahru Nurosyid³

^{1,2,3}Universitas Sebelas Maret, Surakarta, Indonesia

Email: yovitayulianagunawan@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this research was to describe the level of students' critical thinking skills in understanding data sources. The subjects of the research were selected from several public high schools in Surakarta (covering high, medium, and low categories in terms of academic achievement) using cluster random sampling technique. This qualitative research was designed to use a case study approach using descriptive analysis technique to describe the level of students' critical thinking skills. For data collection, this research used the rubric from the International Critical Thinking Essay Test (ICTET) and revealed the following findings: purpose (15.83%), question (13.63%), information (8.63%), point of view (13, 98%), assumptions (5.08%), concepts (6.79%), conclusions (8.90%), and implications (10.62%).

Keywords: *Critical Thinking Skill Level, The Application of Science Concepts, Students' Arguments, ICTET.*

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking skill as the ability to think rationally must be taught to students. All mental activities included in formulating or solving problems, making decisions, or eagerness to understand are stages in thinking (Ruggiero, 1988). Indonesia is implementing the 2013 curriculum in an effort to improve the quality of education. This program places a premium on in-depth comprehension, skill development, and character education. The emphasis of twenty-first-century education is no longer on topic mastery; rather, students are encouraged to integrate information (Lovatt & Finlayson, 2013), make inferences, and even generalize their knowledge in order to develop their style of thinking (Afandi, Sajidan, Akhyar, & Suryani, 2019). Critical thinking skills help students to live in the future (Syahbana, 2012) where they must possess the ability to assess the information they received (Muhamad, Falah, & Windyariani, 2018).

The Next Generation Science Standard (NGSS) affirms that in the future, students must have both critical thinking and communication skills (Mutakinati, Anwari, & Yoshisuke, 2018). Students should not be trapped by the informative learning process since it hinders and gives them the difficulty from in-depth information processing. Students will abandon rationality in favor of memorization (Lunenburg, 2011). Critical thinking is the capacity to examine data, identify its relevance, and interpret data in order to solve issues (Jeevanantham, 2008). Students' replies to critical thinking questions are evaluated using a rubric of reasoning elements that includes the purpose, question, information, point of view, assumptions, concepts, conclusions, and implications (Richard Paul & Elder, 2007). The scientific method emphasized in the 2013 curriculum can be combined with the ICTET's rubric elements to assess students' critical thinking abilities. The 2013 Curriculum's scientific approach contains five basic activities that incorporate the following steps: observing, inquiring, and evaluating, experimenting, associating, and communicating (drawing conclusions, and presenting).

Critical thinking is defined as the ability of speaking confidently by thinking critically which allows students to assess the truth of information. In critical thinking, an organized process occurs, specifically evaluating evidence, assumptions, logic, and language (R Paul & Elder, 2007). The objective of critical thinking is to arrive at a profound understanding. This enables pupils to realize the meaning of an idea, which in turn enables them to comprehend the significance of an event. Constructing scientific arguments is critical practice for students because it teaches them to examine facts from a scientific perspective and within the investigation's conceptual and experimental constraints. (2020; Xing, Lee, & Shibani). Scientific arguments are not comparable to other types of argument (Sampson & Clark, 2008). Scientific reasoning enables scientists and students alike to evaluate evidence gathered throughout the inquiry in order to have a better grasp of the relevant phenomena (Bricker & Bell, 2008). Scientific debate is also one of the eight required scientific practices in the classroom. When students have proposed arguments, the teacher should check the quality of their arguments (Sampson & Clark, 2008).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Students must be able to analyze and evaluate their own thinking in order to improve it. Besides, students can also learn to monitor self-discipline levels by being more sensitive to context and correcting their thinking (Splitter, 1991). There are three important issues to studying how students construct argument in science context: the argument's structure or complexity (i.e., its components), the argument's content (i.e., the accuracy or adequacy of the various components in an argument when evaluated scientifically), and the nature of the justification (how an idea or claim is supported or validated in an argument) (Sampson & Clark, 2008).

Critical thinking is the ability to assess data, identify its relevance, and interpret data in order to solve problems. It necessitates a high degree of thinking that entails analytic, evaluative, logical, and reflective processes (Jeevanantham, 2005). The distinction between low-level learning activities (remembering, comparing, and classifying) and high-level learning activities (assessing credibility, detecting assumptions, and determining the strength of arguments or claims) should become a point of discussion for teachers. (Hager, 1991). Dealing with the demand of the 21st century education, which is critical thinking skills, the ICTET rubric is used to detect students' critical thinking in this research containing eight elements: the purpose, the questions, the facts, the point of view, the assumptions, the concepts, the findings, and the implications are all included.

After receiving information, students will process the information based on their point of view to build assumptions. By combining the concepts that have been learned, students can draw conclusions and think about the implications of the proposed solutions. However, teacher should pay attention to how students build an assumption since they tend to ignore the quality and accuracy of the argument, and do not investigate their points from scientific perspective. Therefore, teacher needs to emphasize the importance of conveying arguments correctly and logically based on scientific concepts. Argumentation is an important aspect to produce, evaluate, and advance scientific knowledge. Thus, it becomes a core component of education. In critical thinking skills, the ability to argue is also pivotal.

Scientists develop their arguments not only verbally, but also via the use of writing, mathematical formulas, illustrations, and photos (Lemke, 1998). Additionally, Lemke asserts that visual representations in scientific publications, such as diagrams, pictures, and graphs, must interpret the complete document, including words, visual representations, and lists of references, in order to comprehend the points stated. According to Lemke's recommendation, the researcher requires students to create brief sketches of their arguments in order to avoid the researcher misinterpreting their reasoning and awarding the correct score. In science education, teachers must consider ways to engage students more deeply in this area so that they can develop the ability to debate scientifically. Teachers must understand that in order for pupils to grow as thinkers, they must progress through many phases of critical thinking. To develop skilled and mature thinkers, educators should structure their activities around the phases of critical thinking, so the expected results can be achieved. Thus, the teachers can estimate the part that must be improved so that students' critical thinking skills develop optimally. In determining the critical thinking skill level of students, the researcher used the reference scores from critical thinking rubric and compared them with criteria of critical thinking development based on stages of critical thinking development (R Paul & Elder, 2007) that are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Scoring of Critical Thinking Development Stages (Paul and Elder, 2009)

Criteria of score	3.51-4.0	Master Thinker
	3.11-3.50	Advanced Thinker
	2.41-3.10	Practicing Thinker
	1.71-2.40	Beginning Thinker
	1.01-1.70	Challenged Thinker
	0-1.0	Unreflective Thinker

Throughout the learning process, data were collected utilizing worksheets and observation sheets. Then, it was examined using a Paul & Elder (2009), Uttal et al. created critical thinking rubric (2012). Paul and Elder's framework for critical thinking is one of the frameworks that some academics use to evaluate critical thinking since it is applicable to engineering, natural sciences, social sciences, and linguistics.

METHODS

The subjects of this research were selected using cluster random sampling from several public high schools in Surakarta which included the high, medium, and low categories in terms of academic achievement. This was a qualitative research using a case study approach. To analyze the data, descriptive method was used to describe the level of students' critical thinking skills. The subjects were 179 students consisting of 4 schools, 8 small classes. During the discussions or experiments, the subjects were divided into 5-6 small groups to enable the researchers to observe the learning process of each group more easily. The approach implemented was the scientific approach which is stated in 2013 curriculum

that It can help students develop a critical, analytical, and precise mindset while identifying, comprehending, solving problems, and applying learning materials (Atsnan & R.Y. Gazali, 2013).

The proper implementation of the 2013 curriculum can sharpen students' critical thinking skills. In developing questions that could measure students' critical thinking, the researcher used a book entitled "Physics by Inquiry" by Lillian C. McDermott, a researcher from the Physics Education Group University of Washington, as a reference. The questions did not only focus on cognitive aspect, but also required students to provide logical solutions of the presented phenomena (some were in the form of videos) and their implications. To answer each question, students were expected to combine all the concepts they had learned.

Table 2 summarizes the critical thinking rubrics based on the International Critical Thinking Essay Test (ICTET) (R Paul & Elder, 2007).

Table 2. Critical Thinking Rubric (based on the Paul-Elder critical thinking framework)

Dimension	Score			
	4	3	2	1
Purpose (A)	Demonstrates a clear understanding of the assignment's purpose.	Demonstrates an understanding of the assignment's purpose.	Is not completely clear about the purpose of the assignment.	Does not clearly understand the purpose of the assignment.
Questions (B)	Clearly defines the issue or problem; accurately identifies the core issues. Appreciates depth and breadth of problem. Demonstrates fair-mindedness toward problem.	Defines the issue; identifies the core issues, but may not fully explore their depth and breadth. Demonstrates fairmindedness.	Defines the issue, but poorly (superficially, narrowly); may overlook some core issues. Has trouble maintaining a fair-minded approach toward the problem.	Fails to clearly define the issue or problem; does not recognize the core issues. Fails to maintain a fair-minded approach toward the problem.
Information (C)	Compiles sufficient, credible, and pertinent data, including observations, claims, logic, data, facts, questions, graphs, themes, assertions, and descriptions. Includes evidence that both opposes and supports the asserted position. Distinguishes between facts and inferences derived from facts.	Collects adequate, credible, and pertinent information. Includes some data from conflicting viewpoints. Distinguishes between facts and inferences based on facts.	Collects some credible data, but not enough; some data may be irrelevant. Significant information is omitted, including some strong counter-arguments. Sometimes confuses information and the inferences drawn from it.	Makes assumptions based on limited, irrelevant, or inaccurate data. Ignores or ignores strong, pertinent counter-arguments. Confuses data and inferences taken from it.
Point of View (D)	Identifies and evaluates relevant significant points of view. Is empathetic, fair in examining all relevant points of view.	Identifies and evaluates relevant points of view. Is fair in examining those views.	May identify other points of view but struggles with maintaining fairmindedness; may focus on irrelevant or insignificant points of view.	Ignores or superficially evaluates alternate points of view. Cannot separate own vested interests and feelings when evaluating other points of view.
Assumptions (E)	Accurately identifies assumptions (things taken for granted).	Identifies assumptions. Makes valid assumptions.	Fails to identify assumptions, or fails to explain	Fails to identify assumptions. Makes invalid assumptions.

Dimension	Score			
	4	3	2	1
	Makes assumptions that are consistent, reasonable, valid.		them, or the assumptions identified are irrelevant, not clearly stated, and or invalid.	
Concepts (F)	Identifies and precisely explains or employs pertinent core concepts.	Identifies, discusses, and applies fundamental concepts properly, but not with the depth and precision of a “4”	Identifies some (but not all) fundamental concepts, but their application is at times cursory and erroneous.	Fundamental concepts are misunderstood or ignored entirely.
Conclusions (G)	Follows where evidence and reason lead in order to obtain defensible, thoughtful, logical conclusions or solutions. Makes deep rather than superficial inferences. Makes inferences that are consistent with one another.	Follows where evidence and reason lead to obtain justifiable, logical conclusions. Makes valid inferences, but not with the same depth and as a “4”	Does follow some evidence to conclusions, but inferences are more often than not unclear, illogical, inconsistent, and/or superficial.	Uses superficial, simplistic, or irrelevant reasons and unjustifiable claims. Makes illogical, inconsistent inferences. Exhibits closed-mindedness or hostility to reason; regardless of the evidence, maintains or defends views based on self-interest.
Implication (H)	Identifies the most significant implications and consequences of the reasoning (whether positive and/or negative). Distinguishes probable from improbable implications.	Identifies significant implications and consequences and distinguishes probable from improbable implications, but not with the same insight and precision as a “4”	Has trouble identifying significant implications and consequences; identifies improbable implications.	Ignores significant implications and consequences of reasoning.

4 = Thinking is exemplary, skilled, marked by excellence in clarity, accuracy, precision, relevance, depth, breadth, logicity, and fairness

3 = Thinking is competent, effective, accurate and clear, but lacks the exemplary depth, precision, and insight of a 4

2 = Thinking is inconsistent, ineffective; shows a lack of consistent competence: is often unclear, imprecise, inaccurate, and superficial

1 = Thinking is unskilled and insufficient, marked by imprecision, lack of clarity, superficiality, illogicality, and inaccuracy, and unfairness

The data collection was analyzed using Kruskal Wallis sequentially to see the differences in critical thinking level in each class. There were several core concepts that students must master: the first, magnetic induction of wire with current; the second, the magnetic force on an electrically current wire and a moving charge; and the third, the application of the principles of magnetic induction and magnetic force in technology in everyday life. In the video presentation, students must be able to predict the impact that would occur when the U magnet was rotated 90 vertically and other questions that required concentration and critical thinking skills. There were also questions that asked students to find ways to distinguish two objects that appeared identical but had different characteristics; magnetic and non-magnetic. Many students could not answer this question well.

Some examples of answers and analysis of students' critical thinking skills levels are presented in Table 3, meanwhile, Table 4 describes the flow of students' thinking in finding solutions so that researchers can classify the stages of their critical thinking skills.

Table 3. Examples of Answers and Analysis of Students' Critical Thinking Skills Level

Students' responses	The level of critical thinking skills
<p>Figure 1. Student A</p>	<p>LOWER (UNREFLECTIVE AND CHALLENGED THINKER)</p>
<p>Analysis of Students' Critical Thinking Skills Level: This problem required students' mastery of Lorentz force concept and the ability to predict the impact that would occur and draw conclusions. The answer provided showed that student A had mastered several elements in the ICTET including purpose, question, and information. The student had a good understanding, so he could sketch the answers that were close to the correct answers. However, when he was challenged to solve problems using relevant concepts and implemented the concepts he had learned, he found it was challenging since there was an overlap between the concepts of electricity and magnetic field. The answers given ended up being distorted and did not have the right implications. There are so many cases of overlapping concepts that trap students in confusion over their own thinking. At this level, the student failed to recognize his thinking which included point of view, assumptions, concepts, conclusions, and implication.</p>	
<p>Figure 2. Student B</p>	<p>AVERAGE (PRACTICING THINKER AND BEGINNING THINKER)</p>
<p>Analysis of Students' Critical Thinking Skills Level: This student had fulfilled the elements in the ICTET that include purpose, question, information, point of view, assumptions, concepts, conclusions, and implication. The answers provided by this student were almost completely correct. This student just misused the term in which he assumed Lorentz force (F) was equal to magnetic field (B). Even though the student's answers were correct and he could describe the sketch well, the teacher should explain that the use of the right concept must also be adjusted to the correct use of the term.</p>	
<p>Figure 3. Student C</p>	<p>LOWER (UNREFLECTIVE AND CHALLENGED THINKER)</p>
<p>Analysis of Students' Critical Thinking Skills Level: This student lacked of detail in providing answers. He had already had good understanding in several stages: purpose, question, and information. The concept he provided was almost correct that could be seen from the second picture. However, the answers related to the point of view, assumptions, conclusions and implication had not well-constructed. Two pieces of iron will attract each other if one of them is magnetic, the written solution will not work. These types of answers were provided by almost 90% of the students. This indicates the low critical thinking skills of students.</p>	
<p>Figure 4. Student D</p>	<p>AVERAGE (PRACTICING THINKER AND BEGINNING THINKER)</p>
<p>Analysis of Students' Critical Thinking Skills Level: This student had understood the purpose, question, information appropriately and had the courage to provide good point of view and assumptions. There is one concept that is well understood, that is, the strongest part of the magnet is the tip, but the student is not consistent in thinking. If a magnetic iron is brought near to a piece of iron, it will always be an attraction, no matter what the student is holding is magnetic iron or common iron. This student is good at one concept but not used to deep thinking. As a result, student who is accustomed to shallow thinking cannot think about implication of the answers given. This must have had an effect on the conclusions made. So it is important for</p>	

teachers to train students to find solutions from different perspectives, do not stuck in one strategy. Shallow thinking is the quickest step to draw the wrong conclusion.

Table 4. Student's Thinking Flow and Stages of Classification of Critical Thinking Skills

Thinking Flow	Conclusion
Stages of Classification: lower (Unreflective and Challenged Thinker)	
<p>The students argued that to lose its magnetic properties, one of the sticks should be dropped in. After that, they would bring the two irons closer, if there was no attractive force, the iron they dropped was a magnet. This process takes a long time because it is not easy to remove the magnetic force of an iron by dropping it. Instead, this also destroys the iron that has been magnetized.</p> <p>*) Unreflective thinkers lack the knowledge that high-quality thinking requires regular practice in taking thinking apart, accurately assessing it, and actively improving it. Unreflective thinkers mostly fail to address their thinking, and the thinkers usually focus on one solution.</p> <p>*) The challenged thinkers have actually developed initial awareness by involving concepts, assumptions, conclusions, implications, points of view, etc in their thinking. But their thinking is still not accurate.</p>	<p>Unreflective thinkers are largely unaware of the appropriate standards for assessment of thinking: clarity, accuracy, precision, relevance, logic, etc. The challenged thinkers already realized that their thinking is often flawed; however, they were not able to identify many of these flaws. Therefore, teachers must recognize the importance of challenging students with supportive learning methods to recognize that they are also thinkers. The teacher must lead the class discussion because most of challenged thinkers have limited skills in thinking.</p>
Stages of Classification : AVERAGE (BEGINNING AND PRACTICING THINKER)	
<p>One example of a student being in the average category as the student's answer which only stopped on the sentence "to get closer to the ends of the magnet". They had tried to think of the right answer, but it was not complete. The students thought that the tip of the magnet is the strong part, but they did not know that the middle part is the weakest part of the magnet.</p> <p>*) Beginning thinkers have enough thinking skills to start monitoring their thinking, even though as "beginners" they are sporadic in that monitoring. Beginning thinkers are able to appreciate a critique of their thinking and have enough intellectual perseverance to struggle with serious problems while yet lacking a clear solutions to those problems.</p> <p>*)Not only do practicing thinkers understand the existence of flaws in their thinking, but they also appreciate the importance of resolving these issues on a global and systematic scale. They actively assess their thinking in a variety of disciplines as a result of their sense of the necessity of practicing constantly. However, because practicing thinkers are only now beginning to pursue thinking improvement in a systematic manner, they have only a limited understanding of deeper levels of thinking.</p>	<p>Beginning thinkers have been able to identify many problems in their thinking but have not found a way to solve them. Beginning thinkers have enough skills in thinking to criticize their own thinking in systematic practice and start monitoring it regularly. Thus they can effectively articulate strengths and weaknesses in their thinking. Practicing thinkers are beginning to recognize egocentric thinking in themselves and others. Practicing thinkers can monitor their thinking about concepts, assumptions, conclusions, implications, points of view, etc.</p>
Stages of Classification: HIGHER (ADVANCE AND MASTER THINKER)	
<p>Whereas for the higher category, called advance thinkers and master thinkers, students must be able to answer that there are two parts of a magnet, see Figure 5a and Figure 5b, the strong part (the ends of the magnet) and the weak part (in the middle of the magnet).</p> <p>Figure 5b. shows if A is magnetic and B is iron, then in the middle part of the image, A will not stick to B (because the middle part of the magnet is very weak)</p> <p>*) Advance thinkers are able to think well but have not been able to think consistently at this high level in all aspects.</p>	<p>Advanced and master thinkers regularly critique their plans. This matter improves their thinking habits thereby. They can combine the information obtained with concepts that have been learned to provide assumptions and convey points of view appropriately. In addition, they are also accustomed to thinking about the implications of their solutions and can provide logical and systematic conclusions based on their way of thinking.</p>

Stage of Critical Thinking Skills of Senior High Schools Students in Indonesia

Note:
 (Higher = M and A; Master Thinker and Advance Thinker),
 (Average = P and B; Practicing Thinker and Beginning Thinker),
 (Lower = C and U; Challenged Thinker and Unreflective Thinker)

Figure 6. Level of Critical Thinking Skills of Senior High Schools Students in Surakarta

By identifying the average level of students' critical thinking skills, the teacher can use the results of this research as a reference. Courage in expressing ideas must be treated fairly and not underestimated by the teacher so that students are more proficient and skilled in critical thinking. In Figure 6, it can be seen that the majority of students are in 2 stages of critical thinking, called unreflective thinkers and challenged thinkers. In more detail, the percentages are presented as follows: Unreflective Thinker 47.49%, Challenged Thinker 39.11%, Beginning Thinker 10.61%, Practicing Thinker 2.79%, while Master and Advance Thinker are still 0%.

Critical thinking is motivated by a sense of wonder and a belief in the evidence's validity. It entails important elements (sometimes referred to as logical reasoning elements), such as the identification of assumptions, the formulation of deliberate inquiries, the pursuit of deeper understanding through reflection, and also the use of perspective (Archibald, Sharrock, Buckley, & Cook, 2016). Students who are trained as critical thinkers are able to work at all levels of higher-order thinking in the cognitive dimension, so that it will impact on improving student learning in terms of understanding, beliefs and new perspectives that are more potential (Mandernach, Forrest, Babutzke, & Manker, 2009).

Level of Critical Thinking Skills of Senior High Schools Students in Surakarta

Note:
 (M and A; Master Thinker and Advance Thinker),
 (P and B; Practicing Thinker and Beginning Thinker),
 (C and U; Challenged Thinker and Unreflective Thinker)

Figure 7. Levels of Critical Thinking Skills in the High School Level in Surakarta

In this research, students' critical thinking levels based on several senior high school are divided into 3 categories, including high, medium, and low levels as shown in Figure 7. SMA A was in high category, SMA B and SMA C were in medium category, and SMA D was in low category. These categories were made based on the average academic achievement of these high schools from 2016-2020. It was assumed earlier that students at SMA A would produce the highest score compared to other high schools because SMA A was a favorite school where students were academically intelligent and quickly learned new things. However, unintentionally, students at SMA D showed the lowest score at the unreflective thinker level. It implies that students at SMA D had unlimited thinking and did not only focus on one solution in answering the proposed questions. SMA D students could develop thinking process that involved concepts, assumptions, conclusions, implications, and points of view better than students from other schools.

The Comparison of Critical Thinking Skills Levels of Indonesian Senior High School Students VS Japanese High School Students

Note:
 (M and A; Master Thinker and Advance Thinker),
 (P and B; Practicing Thinker and Beginning Thinker),
 (C and U; Challenged Thinker and Unreflective Thinker)

Figure 8. Levels of Critical Thinking Skills of Indonesian High School Students VS Japanese High School Students

Based on another research used as a comparison, as shown in figure 8, it is highlighted that junior high school students in Japan (Mutakinati *et al.*, 2018) with a total of 160 students have critical thinking skills which are categorized as advanced thinkers at 41.6%, practicing thinkers at 30.6%, beginning thinkers at 25%, and challenged thinkers at 2.8%. Comparing to Indonesian students, there is a similarity that no one has succeeded in becoming a master thinker. However, there is a significant difference because the percentage of students' critical thinking skills in Indonesia is still dominated by 47.49% of unreflective thinkers and 39.11% of challenged thinkers. This research also employed ICTET to detect students' critical thinking skills. To change students' habit in thinking, teacher needs to design learning process that continuously exposes students to critical thinking activity. The results of this research can be used as a reference by teachers in Indonesia to be able to improve students' critical thinking skills at a higher stage.

CONCLUSION

This research underpins that on average, high school students in Surakarta were included in the lower category (unreflective and challenged thinker) and a small proportion of students were included in the average thinker (beginning and practicing thinker). Those who were average thinkers already had enough thinking skills so that they could assess their plan systematically to strengthen their thinking. Unfortunately, many students lack of knowledge, as a result, they tend to deliver less-logical arguments since they did not incorporate scientific concepts in solving the problems. These arguments will be seen as "stupidity" and will have a detrimental effect on pupils' development of critical thinking skills. Quality thinking needs consistent practice in dissecting, accurately assessing, and actively changing one's thinking.

Thus, from the findings of this research, the researcher address several conclusions: (1) there are predictable stages that each individual who develops as a critical thinker goes through, (2) the development from one stage to the next stage depends on commitment to be critical thinker that it is not automatic or happens unconsciously, and (3) success in teaching is closely related to the intellectual quality of students. Students with higher level of critical thinking can help their friends of the lower level.

The results show that the average score of Indonesian students is in the lower category, so a deeper analysis needs to be developed. For example, at the unreflective thinker and challenged thinker stages, the teacher must be able to make a more detailed rubric to find out the students' mindset so that if a student answers incorrectly, the teacher not only gives a score but also reviews more deeply the level of analysis of the student's critical thinking. At this stage, teachers can find solutions to improve students' critical thinking skills in Indonesia.

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